

IMPORTANT ASPECTS REGARDING THE DEVELOPMENT OF SPEECH COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY SCHOOL LEARNERS

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Abstract. *The given article examines the speech of primary school students, its development, speech competence and its elements. In addition, reference was made to scientists who have conducted research on language development in students and information about aspects considered important in the development of language competencies.*

Keywords: *speech, competence, speech competence, primary grade, speech development, elements of speech competence.*

It is important to suggest that the concepts of language, speech and exchange of ideas are important concepts in human life. This is especially important if a person is in the early years of development. The reason of that for a person, an important life process is the opportunity, as a person develops, to express thoughts, to be able to receive answers to questions that interest him and thereby develop speech and thinking. This process is influenced by parents, educational institutions, educational processes and other factors. One of the main goals of any educational process is to develop students' speech, enrich it with new words, expand their thinking and teach them to express their thoughts fully, freely, and clearly. Since speech is one of the most essential needs of life, it is necessary to create conditions for its improvement in every student.

“Speech development is a very complex and multifactorial process of mastering socio-historical experience, which occupies a central place in the individual development of a child” [2] is a way how D.R. Babaeva describes the work on the development of speech in preschoolers. Speech development is part of the methodology for learning the native language. But this part differs from others in its complexity. That is why a number of linguists in our country have conducted research in this area. M. Askarova, G. Abdullaeva, B. Tokhliev, Sh. Yuldasheva are some of them. Each scientist conducted research on specific stages and aspects of speech development. For example, scientific works written by K. Abdullaeva mainly cover issues of speech development in primary schoolchildren, and a textbook written by M. Askarova is devoted to the studied issues of speech development in preschool children. Because language development is considered a complex and complex process, it also bridges disciplines and fields. Because when working on the development of a student's speech, it is necessary to deal not only with language skills, but also with psychological and physiological aspects.

It is known to everyone that the process of speech development is carried out in a state of division into directions. They are:

1. Work on words;
2. Work on phrases and sentences;
3. Work on coherent speech.[1]

Particularly, these directions are carried out at every stage of education. But developing coherent speech in students is a little difficult. Because, in addition to developing speech and

enriching it with new words, they will have to learn to express thoughts consistently, while maintaining logic. In addition to learning, students learn and master such skills through social and life processes. In such a situation, those who communicate with the student also influence the development of his speech skills and competencies. Competence (lat. *competo* - I strive, I am worthy, I am worthy) - 1) the range of powers, rights and responsibilities of a certain government body (local government body) or official, determined by law, charter or other document; 2) knowledge, experience in a particular area.[3] It is clear from the definition that the word “competence” is a concept used in many areas and with different meanings. In addition, the concept of competence is also used in the field of education. Competence is the ability of students to apply acquired knowledge, experience and innovations in life. That is, a student has acquired some knowledge, this knowledge becomes a competence only after the student has fully assimilated it and consciously applied it in practice. In education, there are 3 main types of competencies, and speech competencies are among the private competencies.

Speech competence includes the following elements:

- Talking
- Reading
- Listening
- Writing

It is obvious that in order for students to acquire and develop speaking competencies, they should pay special attention to each relevant element. For example, in class we studied a text. The teacher should introduce students to this text by assigning tasks or activities through which the students will acquire skills in retelling, reading comprehension, listening comprehension and writing. In this way, you can teach students to remember each subject or information studied well and use it independently in practice.

Undeniably, it should be admitted the importance of emphasizing the role of the teacher in the development of students’ speech competence. Because the teacher must take into account every aspect in the process of organizing a lesson. In addition, we cannot consider the idea that students’ speech should develop only in classes in their native language to be correct. Because students are exposed to many new words and sentences from other subjects. The teacher’s task is to make every concept learned in the lesson understandable to students and bring it to the level of being able to use it outside the lesson. To do this, you can use different methods. The most common of them is to conduct educational games related to the analysis of new concepts and the retention of these concepts in the memory of students.

In order to develop students’ speech competence, special attention should be paid to the following:

- using of types of reading in the process of reading texts (selective reading, role-playing reading, etc.);
- paying special attention to enriching students’ vocabulary (that is, teaching words with their explanations and working on them);
- using more techniques of retelling the text or information being studied;
- using more pictures and exercises during the lesson that develop speech through them;
- using the types of work aimed at developing students’ speech competencies outside of class;

Due to the development of speech competence, students' memory, thinking, perception, sensitivity, accuracy, etc. are simultaneously formed. For example, consider the following exercise. In this case, students are provided with pictures and corresponding words and sentences, and are also given the task of distinguishing these words from the pictures.

Words that can be used are frosty, golden, sunny, changeable, hot. In addition, students can be given the task of composing sentences or short texts using these words. Developing students' speech competence means ensuring their future success. Because having a fully formed speech sets the stage for becoming a leader in any field.

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